

High gamma coherence between task-responsive sensory-motor cortical regions in a motor reaction-time task

<Supplementary Materials>

Supplemental Figure 1. Power spectrum during motor response and baseline after button press. Each trace represents the mean power spectrum across trials ($n = 9902$ trials, units of power in $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$) of all motor-responsive electrodes during the motor response and during the baseline post-button press (red and blue, respectively). Shaded area represents standard error. Characteristic power-law shape with an elbow after 300 Hz validated signal fidelity up to approximately 300 Hz.

Supplemental Figure 2. A) Comparison of ultra-high gamma (170-270 Hz) power and coherence. Plot shows z-scored ultra-high gamma power (blue) and coherence (orange) as a function of time relative to button press ($n = 3457$ trials). Left y-axis shows scale for power, while the right y-axis shows scale for coherence. The black vertical dashed line represents the time of

button press. Ultra-high gamma power and coherence share a more similar time-course than at high gamma frequencies. **B) Ultra-high and high gamma coherence as a function of time and frequency.** Colormap shows a trial-averaged ($n = 3457$ trials) time-frequency coherence plot across all electrode pairs with frequencies from 70 up to 300 Hz. A stronger peak was evident at higher frequencies, with a dampened response after button press. **C) Average time-course of “ultra-high gamma” and high gamma coherence as a function of time.** Plot shows a time-course of “ultra-high gamma” coherence (orange) and high gamma coherence (blue) relative to button press. The shaded region represents standard error. “Ultra-high gamma” coherence peaked on average before high gamma with a higher relative magnitude, while high gamma coherence persisted longer after press. Both began to increase at a similar time before press. Grey, red, and blue bars with stars below x-axis represent time periods uniformly sampled around button press where ultra-high gamma coherence and high gamma coherence were compared with a paired sample t-test. N.S indicates no statistical significance, while *** indicates statistical significance with $p\text{-value} < 0.001$. The p-values for the three comparisons, left to right, were 0.2, $4 \cdot 10^{-22}$, and 10^{-27} , respectively. The color grey indicates no difference, while red/blue indicate whether ultra-high/high-gamma coherence was greater than the other, respectively.

Supplemental Figure 3. Network of sensory-motor high gamma coherence increase during motor response. Cortical area pairs showing statistically significant high gamma coherence change between motor response and baseline with Benjamini-Hochberg multiple comparisons corrections and additional thresholds of a minimum 25% and raw 0.03 coherence increase. Electrodes for each case were localized using individual cortical parcellations. Supplemental Table 3 lists the cortical area pairs shown above.

A**Coherence vs. Power**

B

Coherence vs. Power

Supplemental Figure 4. Average coherence vs. average power across all trials in the three

remaining subjects. Mean power and coherence at baseline (blue circles) and motor response (red circles) for every region-pair and trial ($n = 1188, 1199,$ and 590 trials in S1-S3 respectively) in four canonical frequency bands (**A** shows alpha and low gamma, while **B** shows beta and high gamma) in remaining subjects (S1-S3). Probability density functions at rest (blue) and during motor response (red) are shown for power and coherence at the bottom and left of each plot. Correlation coefficients with p-values and R-squared goodness of fit for all subjects and frequency bands are shown in Supplemental Table 2.

Supplemental Figure 5. Reaction time vs High gamma coherence. Z-scored log reaction time vs Z-scored log high gamma coherence across all region-pairs and trials ($n = 1188, 1199, 590,$ and 480 trials, respectively) across all subjects. No relationship was evident between reaction time and high gamma coherence. Linear fit for each subject shown (red line) with confidence intervals (dotted red line). Correlation coefficient with p-values for the linear fit for S1: $r = -0.17,$ $p < 0.001$; S2: $r = -0.02,$ $p = 0.2$; S3: $r = 0.01,$ $p = 0.69$; and S4: $r = 0.004,$ $p = 0.928$.

Coherence immediately before/after button press, compared to baseline

Supplemental Figure 6. High gamma coherence during 0.5s windows before and after button press. Violin plots show high gamma coherence increase immediately prior to and after button press compared to baseline across all motor-responsive regions and trials (n = 1188, 1199,

and 480 trials, respectively). While a coherence increase is evident even before button press, peak coherence was observed after button press across all subjects.

Locations of high gamma response to button press
without temporal specificity

S1

S2

S3

S4

Locations of high gamma response to auditory stimulus
without temporal specificity

S1

S2

S3

S4

Supplemental Figure 7. Electrode showing high gamma response to button press or auditory stimulus without temporal specificity. Each black dot represents an electrode location from the displayed hemisphere projected onto every subject's cortical surface parcellation. Each red dot represents an electrode with statistically significant high gamma response to button press (top panel) or auditory stimulus (bottom panel). Electrodes in temporal cortex have response to button press and putative sensory-motor cortex have high gamma response to auditory stimulus. This represents the intermediate step of the electrode selection process, without consideration of the timing of high gamma response.

Supplemental Figure 8. Subject-specific high gamma coherence during temporally separated motor and auditory activity. Violin plots show distribution of high gamma coherence

between all motor/auditory-responsive region pairs in each individual subject for all trials (left and right panels respectively). For motor-responsive pairs, coherence was calculated during the 0-0.5 s window after button press, avoiding overlap with the auditory stimulus. For auditory-responsive pairs, coherence was calculated during the window between auditory stimulus presentation and button press, avoiding overlap with the button press. Large and consistent high gamma coherence increases are still observed between motor-responsive regions compared to baseline. The same large and consistent high gamma coherence increase from baseline is not observed between auditory-responsive regions.

High gamma coherence after tactile stimulus presentation

S1

S2

S3

Supplemental Figure 9. High gamma power and coherence in response to tactile stimulus.

Left panel shows the location of high gamma power increases in response to tactile stimulus in three out of four subjects, displayed on subject-specific cortical parcellation (S1-S3, top-to-bottom respectively). Below, we see the high gamma power responses to tactile stimulus, which is indicated by the black dotted line. A number of these regions show high gamma power increases in response to button press, which occurs within a few hundred milliseconds after stimulus onset. Median reaction time was about 200ms (indicated by red #). Right panel shows high gamma coherence between the indicated regions during three periods: tactile stimulus onset to button press (left), 0-0.5 s after button press (center), and 1.5-2 s after button press (right). The area-under-the-curve of the receiver operator characteristic curve between high gamma coherence during tactile stimulus and baseline was calculated with bootstrapping ($n = 1000$). No increase in high gamma coherence is seen in the period between tactile stimulus onset and button press when compared to baseline. An AUC significantly larger than 0.5 would indicate increased coherence during the tactile stimulus window compared to baseline.

Distribution of correlation coefficients between power and coherence across all frequency bands and subjects

Supplemental Figure 10. Correlation coefficients between power and coherence across all putative frequency bands and subjects during button press. Each dot represents the correlation coefficient between power and coherence across all trials in a putative frequency band for a single subject. Red dots specifically represent high gamma coherence and power correlation coefficients. Statistical significance of the correlation is indicated by a symbol on the top-right of the circle, which represents the p-value of the correlation (N.S., *, **, and *** represents $p > 0.05$, $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$, respectively). R^2 values for the linear model fit of high gamma coherence by high gamma power is shown to the right of the red circles that represent the correlation between high gamma power and coherence for the same subject. High gamma power and coherence correlation coefficients are not uniquely different from other frequency bands. Almost all correlation coefficients are statistically significant, even without any coherence changes

taking place in alpha, beta, and low gamma frequency bands, likely due to the large number of trials (n = 1188, 1199, 590, and 480 in S1-S4, respectively).

<Supplemental Table Legends>

Subject	Motor-response locations		
S1	BA1	PFt	
S2	BA1 (x4)		
S3	BA1	FEF	BA3b
S4	BA1 (x2)		

Supplemental Table 1. Location of electrodes determined as motor-task responsive. All subjects had motor-task responsive electrodes in BA1 (8/11 total electrodes across subjects were in BA1). BA and FEF stand for Brodmann Area and frontal eye field, respectively. PFt is a subdivision of the inferior parietal lobule.

BP	Frequency	r	p	R ²
S1	Alpha	0.28	***	0.08
	Beta	0.23	***	0.05
	Gamma	0.02	N.S.	0.0002
	High Gamma	0.10	**	0.01
S2	Alpha	0.24	***	0.1
	Beta	0.19	***	0.04
	Gamma	0.04	**	0.002

AP	Frequency	r	p	R ²
S1	Alpha	0.14	***	0.02
	Beta	0.07	**	0.006
	Gamma	0.07	**	0.006
	High Gamma	0.02	N.S.	0.0006
S2	Alpha	0.37	***	0.1
	Beta	0.17	***	0.03
	Gamma	0.15	***	0.02

	High Gamma	0.25	***	0.06
S3	Alpha	0.22	***	0.05
	Beta	0.21	***	0.04
	Gamma	0.20	***	0.03
	High Gamma	-0.09	***	0.007
S4	Alpha	0.18	**	0.03
	Beta	0.32	***	0.1
	Gamma	-0.02	N.S.	0.003
	High Gamma	0.04	N.S.	0.002

	High Gamma	0.15	***	0.02
S3	Alpha	0.19	***	0.04
	Beta	0.21	***	0.04
	Gamma	0.15	***	0.02
	High Gamma	-0.07	**	0.005
S4	Alpha	0.18	**	0.03
	Beta	0.24	***	0.06
	Gamma	0.10	*	0.01
	High Gamma	0.12	*	0.01

Supplemental Table 2. Correlation coefficients with p-values and R-squared coefficient of determination for all bands and subjects. MP) Button Press AP) After Press. Pearson correlation coefficient with p-values (*, **, *** represents p-values < 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001 respectively) and R-squared goodness of fit for all subjects and analyzed canonical frequency bands.

Subject	Cortical Area Pair	#
S1	BA1 – BA1	4/8
	BA1 – BA2	3/8
	BA2 – BA4	1/8
S2	BA1 – BA1	6/7

	BA1 – BA6v	1/7
S3	BA1 – BA1	3/12
	BA1 – BA3b	3/12
	BA1 – FEF	3/12
	BA2 – BA3b	1/12
	BA2 – FEF	1/12
	BA3b – FEF	1/12
S4	BA1 – BA1	1/4
	BA1 – BA4	1/4
	BA1 – FEF	1/4
	BA1 – BA55b	1/4

Supplemental Table 3. List of cortical region pairs shown in Figure S6 that meet statistical significance and a minimum threshold of 25% and raw 0.03 coherence increase (25% of mean coherence at baseline).